

Fig S1

Fig S2

A**Fig S3**

Table S1. List of antibodies used for immunostaining

Antibodies	Source	Solution
Rabbit anti-Ki67	Abcam	1:500
Rabbit anti-Desmin	Proteintech	1:400
Rabbit anti-Pax3	Abcam	1:500
Rabbit anti-Sox1	Abcam	1:400
Mouse anti-Titin	DSHB	1:50
Mouse anti-MyOD	Santa Cruz Blotechnology	1:250
Mouse anti-Fast Myosin Heavy Chain	Sigma Aldrich	1:100
Mouse anti-MyOG	Santa Cruz Blotechnology	1:500
Mouse anti-Pax7	DSHB	1:100
Rabbit anti-53BP1	Cell Signaling	1:2000
Rabbit anti- γ H2AX	Abcam	1:300
Rabbit anti-Laminin	Abcam	1:500
Mouse anti-MHC	R&D	1:500
Goat anti-T/Bra	R&D	1:250
Mouse anti-Sox2	Santa Cruz Blotechnology	1:400

Table S2. Secondary antibodies used for immunostaining

Antibodies	Source	Solution
Alexa Fluor 594 Goat anti-Rabbit IgG(H+L)	ThermoFisher	1:1500
Alexa Fluor 555 Goat anti-Rabbit IgG(H+L)	ThermoFisher	1:1000
Alexa Fluor 488 Goat anti-Mouse IgG(H+L)	ThermoFisher	1:2000
Alexa Fluor 647 Donkey anti-Goat IgG(H+L)	ThermoFisher	1:1000

Table S3. Primers used for the gene profile analysis by qRT-PCR

Gene	Primers
BRACHYURY-F:	5' CATAAGTATGAGCCTCGAATCC
BRACHYURY-R:	5' GATCTCCTCGTTCTGATAAGCA
PAX3-F:	5' CCTCAGCACCCCAATCAGAT
PAX3-R:	5' TCAAAAGCACGCTCCAGTTC
PAX7-F:	5' AACCACATCCGCCACAAGAT
PAX7-R:	5' CTCTGGTAGCGGCAAAGAA
MYH1-F:	5' GGGAGACCTAAAATTGGCTCAA
MYH1-R:	5' TTGCAGACCGCTCATTTCAA
MYH3-F:	5' CTTGTGGGCGGAGGTCTGG
MYH3-R:	5' AGCTATGCCGAACACTTCCAT
MYH8-F:	5' ACCATGCCAATCGCTTAG
MYH8-R:	5' CAATTGCCAGCTGTTCT
MyOG-F:	5' GTGTGTAAGAGGAAGTCGGTGTC
MyOG-R:	5' GAAGGCCTCATTACCTTCTT
OCT4-F:	5' TGTTCTGCAGTGCCCGAAA
OCT4-R:	5' TTCTGGCGCCGGTTACAGAA
GAPDH-F:	5'GGGAAACTGTGGCGTGAT
GAPDH-R:	5'GAGTGGGTGTCGCTGTTGA